

Volume 1, Issue 1, 2024

***RELATIONS OF STUNTING WITH THE DEVELOPMENT LEVEL OF
BADUTA IN EX-GAKY ENDEMIC REGIONS, BUNTU BATU DISTRICT,
ENREKANG REGENCY***

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ABSTRACT

Stunting is closely associated with impaired growth and development. However, in Enrekang Regency, which is known to have a high prevalence of stunting, human development is actually very good, as evidenced by the Human Development Index (HDI) which is the second highest in South Sulawesi. It is suspected that there are other factors that play a role in this, namely IDD because in 2003 it was an endemic area for IDD. The current unknown status of IDD and the high prevalence of stunting while the HDI is good are the basis for conducting research regarding the relationship between stunting and the level of development of IDD in ex-IDD endemic areas. This research uses a cross-sectional research design. The development of the sample, namely baduta, was measured using the Pre-Screening Development Questionnaire (KPSP).and descriptive analysis was carried out using SPSS. The result obtained is thatThe prevalence of stunting among Baduta in Buntu Batu District is quite high, namely 48.5%. The prevalence of IDD among Baduta mothers in Buntu Batu District is 42%. The level of development of Baduta (Motoric, Personal Social, Speech and language as well as Socialization and Independence) in Buntu Batu District is normal at 44 (45.4%), suspect 31 (32%) and deviant 22 (22.6%). From the research results it can be concluded that there is no relationship between stunting and the level of development of Baduta in Buntu Batu District with a p-value = 0.083

Keywords: Stunting, Development, IDD

INTRODUCTION

Child development is all changes that occur in the child including all physical, motoric, personal, social, language and speech, social and independence changes.¹ According to the WHO (World Health Organization), more than 200 million children under 5 years old, including toddlers, in the world do not fulfill their development potential and most of them are children who live on the continents of Asia and Africa. National data according to the Indonesian Ministry of Health shows that in 2014, 13% - 18% of children under five, including children under five, experienced growth and development disorders.²

Many factors play an important role in supporting physical growth and development, one of which is nutritional factors. The problem of malnutrition that is vulnerable to development is poor nutritional status and short nutritional status or what is now better known as stunting³. Children with stunting will experience delays or failure in growth and development. One of the causes of stunting is IDD (Iodine Deficiency Disorder), it is known that iodine regulates thyroid hormone which works in growth and development hormones. (Sumartini, 2020). Child development can be measured, one of them is by using the KPSP (Pre-Screening Development Questionnaire), this instrument is used as a tool to detect deviations in child development including motor development, personal social, speech and language as well as socialization and independence.⁴

Based on several previous studies by Yeni Iswari in 2021 in Karawang, it shows that there is a relationship between nutritional status and the development of children aged 0-24 months, The better the nutritional status, the more appropriate the child's development level is according to his age. Other research related to developmental screening by Hardiana Probosiwi in 2017 on children 12-60 months old showed that there was a relationship between stunting and toddler development, children with stunting had a 3.9 times greater risk of having stunted development compared to children who were not stunted. However, one area in South Sulawesi is quite different and attracts

attention, namely Enrekang Regency. Enrekang Regency is the district with the highest prevalence of stunting in South Sulawesi. Based on Riskesdas data, the prevalence increased from 42.7% in 2018 to 43.71% in 2019⁵. The high prevalence of stunting in Enrekang Regency is inversely proportional to the level of human development. Based on 2020 Health Service data, Enrekang Regency's Human Development Index (HDI) ranks second highest in South Sulawesi, namely 72.15% and is above the South Sulawesi HDI average. Correlation tests for HDI variables and stunting carried out in all districts in South Sulawesi showed that there was no significant relationship, while if we excluded Enrekang District, we found a significant negative correlation ($p=0.051$, $r=0.442$), meaning that the higher the HDI score, the higher low stunting. From existing theories and data, it is suspected that there are other factors that play a role, it is also suspected that this factor is IDD, considering that previously based on the 2003 IDD Survey, Enrekang Regency was one of the two areas with the highest endemic IDD in Indonesia. Due to the high prevalence of stunting and the unknown current status of IDD, it is an important concern to understand the relationship between stunting and development in former IDD endemic areas. In line with this, ICONS FKM Unhas also conducted research related to IDD and stunting in Buntu Batu District, Enrekang Regency, as the District with the highest prevalence of stunting. So, in conjunction with the ICONS FKM Unhas research, researchers want to research the relationship between stunting and the level of development of young people in former endemic IDD areas.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research uses a cross-sectional research design. This research was carried out in a former endemic IDD area, namely in Buntu Batu District, Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi. The implementation time is July – December 2021. The population in this study are all baduta whose parents are from Enrekang and live in Buntu Batu District. The sample in this study were baduta whose parents were from Enrekang and lived in Buntu Batu sub-district. The sampling technique is purposive sampling by determining inclusion and exclusion criteria. The entire sample is 96 samples of baduta aged 0-24 months so that for informed consent the research and interview process was carried out with the baduta's mother. The respondents, namely baduta mothers, were interviewed for approximately 25 minutes in one meeting. Apart from that, researchers make observations or external observations of behavior to verify the information provided by respondents. Data collection was carried out during the COVID-19 pandemic so that activities in

the field were carried out with health protocols. Researchers wear masks and always use hand sanitizer. Before the interview, respondents were also given masks to further improve health protocols. The instruments used in this research were anthropometric tools, writing tools, urine collection containers, KPSP questionnaires, KPSP assistive toys and SPSS software.

RESULTS

Buntu Batu District is one of the 12 sub-districts in Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi. This sub-district is approximately 53 kilometers (Km) from the capital city of Enrekang Regency. It can be reached using two wheels or four wheels in around 1 hour 50 minutes from Enrekang City. The population in Buntu Batu District based on 2019 BPS (Central Statistics Agency) data reached 13,842 people, 7,080 men and 6,762 women. The geographical condition of Buntu Batu District is at a land height of 100-1700 m above sea level. With hilly and mountainous topography and the boundary area of Buntu Batu District is 126.65 km². The research was conducted in 3 stunting locus villages in Buntu Batu District, namely Buntu Mondong Village, Potokullin Village and Latimojong Village.

As for the results of the research which was carried out from July to December 2021 in Buntu Batu District, which included collecting primary and secondary data as well as data processing and analysis, the following results were obtained:

1. Sample Characteristics

The research results based on the characteristics of the baduta as a sample, namely gender, age and iodine excretion of the baduta's mother, are then presented in the table.

Table 1. Results of Univariate Analysis of Baduta Characteristics

Child Characteristics	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Gender		
Man	52	53.6
Woman	45	46.4
Age		
1	9	9.3
2	4	4.1

3	4	4.1
4	5	5.2
5	6	6.2
6	4	4.1
8	3	3.1
9	3	3.1
10	5	5.2
11	3	3.1
13	9	9.3
14	3	3.1
15	7	7.2
16	7	7.2
18	2	2.1
19	7	7.2
20	6	6.2
21	3	3.1
22	3	3.1
23	4	4.1
Total	97	100.0

Source: Secondary Data, 2021

Based on table 5.1, it shows that 52 (53.6%) of the samples were male and 45 (46.4%) were female. Based on the age of the samples, the largest were 1 month and 13 months, namely 9 samples each (9.3%) and the ones that were missing were samples aged 7, 12, 17 months and 24 months.

2. Stunting

Table 2. Results of Univariate Analysis of Baduta Nutritional Status

Nutritional Status (PB/U)	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Normal	50	51.5
Stunting	47	48.5
Total	97	100.0

Source: Secondary Data, 2021

Based on table 5.2, it shows that baduta with normal nutritional status in terms of body length according to age are 50 (51.5%), while baduta with stunted nutritional status are 47 (48.5%).

3. Development

Table 3. Results of Univariate Analysis of Baduta Development Levels

Development Status	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
Normal	44	45.4
<i>Suspect</i>	31	32
Digress	22	22.6
Total	97	100

Source: Secondary Data, 2021

Based on table 5.3, it shows that there are 44 (45.4%) baduta with a normal level of development, 31 (32%) with suspect development and 22 (22.6%) with deviant development.

4. IDD

Table 4. Results of Univariate Analysis of IDD Incidence

Maternal Iodine Excretion Status	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)
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Enough	53	54.6
Not enough	41	42.3
Hyperthyroid	3	3.1
Total	97	100

Source: Secondary Data, 2021

IDD is still considered a public health problem in Indonesia, because in general the prevalence of IDD in 2010 was still above 5% and varied between regions, where we still found sub-districts with IDD prevalence above 30%. (Riskesdas, 2010). Based on the results of research on urinary iodine excretion of toddler mothers, 55 (55%) had sufficient iodine status, 42 (42%) had deficient iodine status and 3 (3%) were hyperthyroid. So it can be said that in this area there are still remnants of endemic IDD because the prevalence is still high.

5. The Relationship between Stunting and Development

Table 5. Results of Bivariate Analysis of the Relationship between Stunting and Development

Nutritional Status (Stunting)	Development Status			Total	p*
	Digress	Suspect	Normal		
Stunting	8	20	19	47	0.083
%	17%	42.6%	40.4%	100%	
Normal	14	11	25	50	(person chi square)
%	28%	22%	50%	100%	
Total	22	31	44	97	
%	22.6%	32%	45.4%	100%	

Source: SPSS Analysis, 2021

Based on table 5.5, it shows that the total sample was 97 people. The sample who experienced stunting was 47 people. Of the 47 people, 8 people experienced deviant development, 20 experienced suspect development and 19 people had normal development. Meanwhile, there are 50 children with normal nutritional status or not stunted. Of the 50 people, 14 people experienced deviant development, 11 people experienced suspect

development and 25 people had normal development. Based on testing using the chi square test in SPSS, the significance value was $p = 0.083$. The value obtained is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. So the interpretation of the test results is not significant, that is, there is no significant relationship between stunting and development.

DISCUSSION

This research aims to see the relationship between stunting and the level of development of young people in former endemic IDD areas, namely in Buntu Batu District, Enrekang Regency.

1. Respondent Characteristics

Respondents in this study were parents of toddlers (babies aged two years / 0-24 months) who were interviewed and held discussions while the toddlers were the research sample. The respondent is a native of Enrekang and lives in Buntu Batu District. Baduta is the age of 1000 HPK (First day of life) which is often called the golden age period. This is because this age is the age when a child's growth and development is very rapid and determines the child's growth and development in the following period. The sample consisted of more men than women with different ages ranging from 0-24 months.

2. Stunting

Stunting is a chronic nutritional problem in toddlers which is characterized by shorter height compared to children their age. Children who suffer from stunting will be more susceptible to disease and as adults are at risk of developing degenerative diseases. The impact of stunting is not only on health but also affects children's intelligence levels.⁶

Based on the research results, it can be seen that clowns who experience stunting are 48.5% of the total sample. From this percentage, the stunting rate in Enrekang Regency is still very high when referring to the WHO standard, namely 20%.

According to data from the Ministry of Health's Basic Health Research (Riskesmas), the national stunting rate has decreased from 37.2% in 2013 to 30.8% in 2018. According to the Indonesian Toddler Nutrition Status Survey (SSGBI) in 2019, this figure decreased to 27.7%. Reducing stunting rates has been declared a national priority program. Currently, the Government continues to move to organize implementation tools to accelerate stunting

prevention and prepare a National Strategy (Stranas) for the Acceleration of Prevention of Stunting for 2018-2024. The government, through the National Medium Term Development Plan (RPJMN) 2020-2024, has also set a target for the national stunting rate to fall to 14%.

3. Development

Development is the process by which an individual grows and changes throughout the life cycle. Or refers to the qualitative changes that begin at conception and continue through the lifespan. for example the ability to sit, stand, walk, learn to speak and so on. In the words of Elizabeth Hurlock, "the term development means a series of progressive changes that occur in a regularly predictable pattern as a result of maturation and experience." According to Crow and Crow, "growth refers to structural and physiological changes and development is related to growth and changes resulting from the environment".

Based on the research results, it shows that there are 44 (45.4%) baduta with a normal level of development, 31 (32%) with suspect development and 22 (22.6%) with deviant development.

Development is the increasing structure and function of the body which is more complex in the ability of gross movement, fine movement, speech and language as well as socialization and independence. Development is the result of the interaction of the maturity of the central nervous system with the organs it influences, for example the development of the neuromuscular system, speech abilities, emotions and socialization. All of these functions play an important role in a complete human life.⁷.

4. IDD

Respondents had different iodine excretion status, as many as 42% of respondents had deficient iodine excretion status (IDD). The iodine excretion status of the respondent (the baduta's mother) can be used to see whether the area still has remaining IDD or not, because previously IDD was endemic. IDD is a group of symptoms that arise because a person's body lacks the element iodine. In the human body, iodine is needed to form the hormone thyroxine which is needed by the body to regulate growth and development from fetus to adult.⁸

Many factors also play a role in the incidence of IDD, including genetic factors, gene mutations, environmental damage which causes many minerals in the soil to be lost and consumption of goitrogenic substances. Iodine is an essential nutrient that is found in very small amounts in the body. Iodine is part of the thyroxine hormone which functions in regulating child growth and development. Iodine metabolism is related to growth hormone (GH) which has an important role in growth. The results of iodine metabolism have a function in the rate of nutrient metabolism, nutrient transportation, etc. If iodine deficiency occurs, it will indirectly cause thyroid hormone deficiency and growth hormone deficiency. This can disrupt the growth and metabolism of nutrients in the body, such as disrupting cell growth or the function of other nutrients. Iodine deficiency can cause disruption of growth and development, such as cretinism and decreased intelligence. Thyroid hormones also influence epiphyseal growth, bone maturation and height (body length). Thyroid hormones control the speed at which each cell uses oxygen and control the speed at which energy is released from nutrients that produce energy. Thyroxine can stimulate protein and carbohydrate metabolism by up to 30 percent. Children born and living in IDD endemic areas have relatively difficulty accessing local food containing iodine so they are at greater risk of experiencing IDD or iodine deficiency (Putri Tiara Nur Mahardika, 2019).

Iodine is a trace mineral that is essential for normal growth and development. Iodine deficiency causes retardation or delays in growth, mental development, and maturity of organ systems (secretion of T3 and T4) which play a role in the growth process, causing failure to thrive in children under five years of age.⁹

5. The Relationship between Stunting and Development

Stunted children are more likely to become sick due to immune deficiency status and sick children are more likely to be stunted in growth and development due to poor nutritional absorption.¹⁰ The domain of child development consists of gross motor skills, fine motor skills, language and speech, and personal social/independence. Malnutrition will hinder the rate of child development. As a result, the proportions of the body structure become inappropriate for age and this has implications for the development of other aspects. Evidence shows that the period from pregnancy to the first 2 years of life (known as the first 1,000 days)

is a critical period for preventing malnutrition, because after a child's second birthday, it becomes increasingly difficult to improve growth and prevent stunting.¹¹ The majority of a child's brain development is complete by age 2 and malnutrition during this time increases the risk of developmental and cognitive delays in children. Hypothesis testing shows that there is a statistically significant relationship between nutritional status and development. Toddlers who have nutritional status with normal stature are 3.3 times more likely to have appropriate development ($b=3.33$; $p=0.003$).¹²

Several studies have found a link between height growth and developmental changes in the first 2 years of age. Animal studies show that the cerebellum of the brain, which coordinates motor movements, is the part that is most susceptible to damage during infancy, so that malnutrition early in a child's life will hinder motor development. Children who are stunted are thought to have low motor activity. Child development experts believe that motor activity during the second year plays an important role in the development of children's competence. (Pantaleon, et al, 2015)

Based on the research results, it shows that the total sample was 97 people. The sample who experienced stunting was 47 people. Of the 47 people, 8 people experienced deviant development, 20 experienced suspect development and 19 people had normal development. Meanwhile, there are 50 children with normal nutritional status or not stunted. Of the 50 people, 14 people experienced deviant development, 11 people experienced suspect development and 25 people had normal development.

Stunting at the age of 0-2 years can disrupt children's cognitive, language and motor development (Muhoozi: 2016). Around 16% of Indonesian toddlers experience developmental disorders, including brain development disorders, hearing disorders and motor disorders and in 2010 it reached 35.7% including developmental disorders which can be seen from the incidence of speech and language disorders in Indonesian children which is still high, namely 2.3% - 24.6% and the prevalence of speech and language delays in school children is 5-10% (Suparmiati, 2013)

Based on the results of the research, testing was then carried out using the chi square test in SPSS, obtaining a significance value of $p=0.083$. The value obtained is greater than the

alpha value of 0.05. So the interpretation of the test results is not significant, that is, there is no significant relationship between stunting and development. These results are quite different from several theories that have been explained previously and several previous studies. Research conducted by¹³in Central Java Province shows that there is a significant relationship between stunting and gross motor and fine motor development. That stunted children tend to have hampered motor development, both gross and fine motor skills.

Other research states that developmental delay disorders are characterized, among other things, by slow maturity of nerve cells, slow motor movements, lack of intelligence, and slow social responses. In the short term, stunting can cause failure to thrive, obstacles to cognitive & motor development, thus affecting brain development and educational success, and suboptimal physical body size and metabolic disorders. Children experiencing stunting have the potential for imperfect growth and development, low motor skills and productivity, and have a higher risk of suffering from non-communicable diseases. Stunting in toddlers results in potential economic losses due to reduced work productivity and care costs. All of this will reduce the quality of human resources, productivity and the nation's competitiveness.¹⁴

Similar research was carried out by Maria Goreti et al in 2015 in Yogyakarta which stated that there was a significant relationship between stunting and the motor development of toddlers ($p=0.002$), but there was no significant relationship between stunting and the language, socio-emotional and adaptive development of toddlers. This is in line with research by Hardiana Probosiwi et al in Sleman in 2017 which stated that there was a significant relationship ($p<0.05$) and an OR value of 3.9 (95% CI; 1.7-8.9). Other research that also supports the results of research on stunting and child development is research by Mirham Nurul, et al in West Nusa Tenggara in 2018 which states that toddlers with normal stature have a 3.3 times chance of experiencing appropriate development compared to children with short and very short stature (stunting). Based on theoretical studies and several previous studies as explained above, the results of this study are quite different from most other research results. This is because in Enrekang Regency, apart from the high prevalence of stunting, the IDD rate is also high. Ignorance is a risk factor for stunting in Enrekang Regency outside of the risk factors in the WHO conceptual framework. However, if you look at the Human Development

Index data, Enrekang Regency is quite high and is the Regency with the second highest Human Development Index data in South Sulawesi, the results of this research are in accordance with this data, where in Enrekang Regency the high rate of stunting has no effect on development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results obtained, it can be concluded that the prevalence of stunting among Baduta in Buntu Batu District is quite high, namely 48.5%. The prevalence of IDD among Baduta mothers in Buntu Batu District is 42%. The level of development of Baduta (Motoric, Personal Social, Speech and language as well as Socialization and Independence) in Buntu Batu District is normal at 44 (45.4%), suspect 31 (32%) and deviant 22 (22.6%). And overall it is known that there is no relationship between stunting and the level of development of Baduta in Buntu Batu District with a p-value = 0.083.

The results of this research only show how stunting and development are related. Meanwhile regarding IDD, just look at whether there are still IDD or not. Therefore, it would be better if further research could be carried out looking at the extent to which IDD influences stunting and the extent to which IDD influences stunting and the development of Baduta in Buntu Batu District, Enrekang Regency.

THANK-YOU NOTE

The implementation of this research was able to run smoothly with the help of many parties, so on this occasion the researcher would like to express many thanks to 1) Thank you to ICONS FKM Unhas 2) Thank you to the Buntu Batu District Health Center 3) Thank you to the Nutrition Science Study Program Unhas 4) Thank you thank you to family, friends and comrades in arms in research 5) Thank you to the people of Buntu Batu, especially the villages of Buntu Mondong, Potokullin and Lantimojong.

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